

Social Capital at the Rescue of Poor Elderly

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[Aging is golden or aging is gray. It connotes the living experiences in two different worlds. The rich getting richer and enters into the later life signifies a better living. Though the question of familial ties and ties beyond family related to happiness is still questioned. But for a poverty struck the income hardship along with material hardship creates a major threat to the satisfaction of life of poor elderly. United Nations for Aging Income Poverty in Old Age gives a remark on elderly those who are having greater probability to remain poor at times in spite of crossing the age of 60 they still continue to work. Even on lower wages than before. The safety nets available in developing world guarantees a meager amount but perhaps not the quality of life. This makes the elderly population vulnerable to economic insecurity also leading to food insecurity and shelter hardship. Sometimes they have cumulative effect on well-being of the elderly while at the other times in isolation, they also influence their multidimensional well-being. Poverty breeds better relationship within family due to sympathy and similar economic position. But 'Is this relationship enough?' to bring out of the poverty trap and 'Do they have bridging relationship?' to push them out of this remains an intriguing question.]

Accuracy of the data provided on poverty on elderly is difficult to trust. The estimates and parameter on measures of poverty in different regions of the world are so much varied that their comparison is not justifiable. So, the problem of enumeration and level of problem of poverty remains elusive (social.un.org/ageing). There is no database on old age poverty with respect to age cohorts so that one can delve into it with seriousness of changing experiences along with aging. At present documents on poverty related to elderly is published by selected countries (World Population Ageing Report UN statistics division, 2015). According to the recent data published on elderly above the age of 60 years related to poverty, it is seen that in Netherland it is just 2% in 2013, in Czech Republic it is 3% in 2012 while in Australia it has astonishing figure of 34%. Looking at it as a developed world it may be due to the stricter parameters of measuring poverty and a higher level of definition of poverty that may have included elderly up to this extent. On the other side, Republic of Korea has 50% of its elderly population as poverty struck.

The figure of Zambia in 2005 informs a lot about the plight of elderly in most part of African continent. The whooping figure of poverty of elderly in Zambia has reached to 80%. This data clearly finds gap in the two worlds of golden years and gray years. But this is not the complete story. Forbes publishes data on richest person not the happiest person. There is much to unfold in both the worlds.

Aging decreases the participation in workforce. The manual workers relying on health and engaged in informal sector bears the most brunt. Within Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) the gap of poverty level is quite high. It is not a regional problem based on location of the community but among the cohorts within the countries there is wide difference. The persons living in these countries as elderly aged 66 to 75 years are struck with poverty figures as 11.2% while aged over 75 years are struck with 14.7%. It indicates that elderlies are not a homogeneous group and it requires further interpretation and deeper insight to resolve the problem that exist with the rising age. There is always a chance and opportunities for elderly aged 60 to 75 who could continue to work after 60 trying to come out of the poverty trap and in a way not succumbing but those who are aged above 80 usually known as oldest old in all the probabilities, they have lesser to contribute in the workforce and in the most likelihood, they have exhausted their savings. They are in dire need of safety nets that extends from income to health. The state of Uttar Pradesh in India has dealt differently to the aged over 80 realizing that they have different experiences and different status of health than earlier cohorts They get pension amount twice the amount of above 60 years and falling below poverty line. The aged above 80 years requires different policy and safety net than all other cohorts.

The whole world is experiencing faster growth in oldest old in last decade than what it had been earlier. The fraction of aged above 80 is increasing its share among aged 60 plus. It has also been projected that this could increase to thrice of the present to become half billion by 2050.

As the experiences of different cohorts differ so is older women are more vulnerable than older men. Their literacy and patriarchy hamper their access to safety net and health services. The access to the formal world of Social Security is restricted due to existing gender inequalities. Sometimes the life expectancy of women even in developing world is quoted to be higher than men. This create deeper problem during widowhood to participate in workforce even for the women who had never been part of it earlier to her 60s. Pension policies have not dealt differently to the widows in 60s. World population ageing report remarks about endemic nature of poverty especially for those who have their youth and adulthood spent in poverty are more prone to face deepening poverty in their later life (Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing, para. 45, 2002). United Nations report on ageing women's labor force participation also concludes that the women are mostly self-employed and even those who are in informal or formal services they have interrupted career due to child rearing and caring. The natural enhancement of being motherly results into a bitter payment of struck into poverty. The contributions made during, even for contributory pension is far less than a male counterpart because of her short journey of career.

When the number of choices increases women is termed as empowered. Further, this empowerment is exclusively seen in decision making but these stories from sub-Saharan Africa is different. The researchers have found that there are elderly women who are heads of the family can be single, divorced and widowed but more fragile to fall into the trap of poverty. The case is no different in developed world. The probability of being in poverty is relatively higher for women than men. It has also been seen that women survive on survivors' benefit gained due to husband's contribution in pension or else.

Sustainable development goals Agenda for Sustainable Development (2030) envisaged in its document to end poverty in all its varied forms and from all communities tend to incorporate and emphasized to enhance the life of elderly who is poor also. It asserts the problem of policy to address the problem of old age poverty. As clearly mentioned, that incoming fourth decade the aged population will double and the figure will be staggering at 2.1 billion. The sustainable development goals project the figure of elderly to cross the 1 billion marks in developing world by 2030. The constraint of resources of the developing world creates deep problem to allocate for elderly. The cost of infrastructure to be developed, for youth to be utilized as resources and nurturing childhood to become resources is already escalating amidst carrying forward elderly as the least resourceful in terms of monetary is a herculean task to be addressed. The problem of elderly living in poverty is more emphatic in developing world

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where safety nets are under constraints of resources to cater the needs of the ageing elderly.

Traditional societies such as India have survived on familial support to assist the living of elderly but the dawn of industrialization and ever-increasing urbanization has taken a heavy toll of familial ties and life in community. Villages were known as little community having everything for everyone. But the search for employment led to the migration leaving behind elderly in isolation. The problem escalates when formal support is meagre. Even in communities which were less developed were having high social capital to support elderly but with the increase in socio economic pressure, trend towards consumption, increased longevity and failing family ties have resulted in number of elderly falling into the perilous trap of poverty. The need for policy interventions is tremendous to focus on security pension as necessity and health interventions should be dealt in integration. It should also find a place of social capital in the lives of elderly as man is the product of socio psycho drives should be dealt relevantly. Traditional societies with meagre amount should also focus on familial ties within their policy making. However, it is important to re-emphasize that they are elderly and poor also who have still not been covered under safety nets where it is already available. (World Population Ageing Report,2015).

World Social Protection Report (2015) commented on need of protection of elderly in poverty health trap. Income security in old age is the product of old age pension available through safety nets and schemes that promotes easy access to secure and affordable services that relates to health. The affordability of Health Services in a way adjusts for the income hardship. The out of pocket of elderly looking after ones own health should be dissolved as quicker as possible. In India Ayushman Card have done tremendous services to the majority of persons facing hardships in many respects. Sufficient nutritious food available through public distribution system has also helped millions to live on meagre amount of pension or their own employment. It is also a virtual safety net for family in which they live. Even in European countries elderly have been forced to spend, sometimes, around 25% of their household income. The dying intergenerational ties have disabled intergenerational transfers which was used for their health or services which are not available through safety net. Traditional societies have managed elderly in their own environment by taking care ageing in place. But the changes that has occurred in societies such as India have generated tremendous pressure on the subjective experiences of elderly in situ and also on policy makers to allocate more and more resources for elderly who has no more potential to contribute emphatically in the economy.

The effectiveness of safety net program on income-based, food-based or health-based in context as it has been observed this similar program has flourished in a different location but failed to make effective impact on different location (Baum FE,2003). WHO envisaged that there are social determinants of health. Here it is pointed that it is social capital that has theoretical basis to promote health. If it is intertwined along with similar enhancing health well-being for poor, elderly can get non-tangible impetus. For Coleman (1990) in Foundations of Social Theory opined that it facilitates actions of individuals and for Putnam (1993) in Making Democracy Work opined that it is trust, norms and networks that facilitates. Social capital can be understood in different dimensions such as structural and cognitive. Promotion of this type of structural dimension of social capital, along with other safety nets via civic engagement and social participation promotes health. The cognitive dimension connotes subjective experiences in form of trust. Researchers have observed trust to have influence on health and well-being. So, this also could be incorporated along with material services via safety nets to promote health and well-being effectively.

Family ties have been fragile in traditional societies also and formal support being already weak, it meant more vulnerability for poor elderly. Bonding social capital refers to relations within homogeneous entities. This may be quite effectively used as an informant if one is already literate with financial and other information that results in enhancement of wellbeing of elderly. Bonding relationship could provide good communication to utilize, the already existing services in a community. Bridging social capital refers to relationship between individuals of different hierarchy levels. It has been seen that those

who have bridging social capital are in a better position with respect to their well-being than their counterparts.

Kawachi and Berkman (2000) are known for their work (Social cohesion, social capital, and health) on social capital and health, they have concluded with eight field where social capital could be utilized to have better outcomes within that community life and public health have also been discussed. Kawachi et al (2006) give number of evidences that finds links between social capital and health (Making the Connections One Step at a Time). Social capital has been utilized at four levels (Macinko J, Starfield B.,2001) at macro level they have discussed countries, regions, states municipalities, at micro level they have discussed about social network and social participation while at individual level, they have stressed on trust and norms. Usually, the emphasis is on contextual impact of social capital on individual health.

Another clue from the Kawachi and Berkman (2000) study that can be incorporated into policy making for poor elderly is that they have widely discussed the mechanism between social capital and health. It can be utilized for providing information about health promoting norms through informal control promoting services and evolve mutual respect. All these can contribute to poor elderly in a non-tangible way though a fraction of amount could be invested on promoting such relationship. Social capital can act as a cushion for elderly who is poor and carve out a relatively better path of well-being.

Now it is seen that the geriatric population in developing and developed world, though have different experiences but they are demographic burden. The policies in yesteryears in both the world have allocated resources for their upliftment but the double jeopardy of being aged and poor too has immense repercussions on their health and well-being. These social changes that have taken place in last two centuries and especially in last 50 years in form of industrialization, urbanization, migration, fragile joint family, in hygienic living spaces and ever-increasing generation gap have certainly been not met with such emphasis to recover the poor elderly from falling into poverty health trap. There is need of a holistic approach and need of plethora of non-financial efforts to rejuvenate them from their fragile condition.

The policies should embark to counter varied types of hardships that poor elderly face through integrated approach of monetary, food, health, shelter and relationship building measures. The beauty lies in approaching a human being as a multi-dimensional being. The incorporation of all-in-one window, one application and one program for elderly could take miles forward.

Reference

1. Pensions at a Glance 2015: OECD and G20 Indicators UNDESA (2015)
2. Department of Economic and Social Affairs programme on ageing The focal point on ageing in the United Nations system social.un.org/ageing
3. World Population Ageing Report UN statistics division (2015)
4. Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing, para. 45 Department of Economic and Social Affairs programme on ageing
5. Agenda for Sustainable Development (2030)
6. World Social Protection Report 13 WHO (2015), World Report on Ageing and Health 14 A/68/167 15 WHO (2015)
7. Baum FE. The effectiveness of community-based health promotion in Healthy Cities programmes. In: Takano T, editor. Healthy cities & urban policy research. London: Spon Press; 2003
8. Coleman JS. Foundations of social theory. Massachusetts: Harvard University Press; 1990.
9. Putnam RD. Making democracy work: civic traditions in modern Italy. New Jersey: Princeton University Press; 1993.
10. Kawachi I. Commentary: social capital and health: making the connections one step at a time. Int J Epidemiology. 2006
11. Kawachi I, Berkman LF. Social cohesion, social capital, and health. In: Berkman LF, Kawachi I, editors. Social epidemiology. New York: Oxford University Press; 2000.
12. Macinko J, Starfield B. The utility of social capital in research on health determinants. Milbank Q. 2001

